

**The first record of a tephritoid fly
(Diptera: Tephritoidea: Ulidiidae)
from the Republic of San Marino**

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The genus *Herina* is represented in Europe by 16 species of the picture-winged flies occurring throughout Europe, except Iceland, Land of Franz-Josef Land, Novaja Zemlya; they have not been recorded from Luxemburg, Liechtenstein, Vatican, Belarus, Moldova and some island territories, as well as from Kaliningrad Region of Russia, due to the lack of material. In addition, no species of the superfamily Tephritoidea have been ever recorded from the Republic of San Marino (Kameneva, 2007; Kameneva & Greve, 2011; Pape & Beuk, 2011). Occasionally, two specimens of a picture-winged flies were found among undetermined materials in the collection of Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin (MNKB):

***Herina rivosecchii* Merz, 2002**

Material examined: San Marino, 21.08.1912, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (R. Reymonds leg.) (MNKB).

Distribution: Croatia, Czech Republic, France (incl. Corsica), Greece (mainland, Crete), Italy (mainland, Sicily), Slovakia, and Switzerland (Kameneva, 2007; Kameneva & Greve, 2011); San Marino (first record).

Figs 1–3: *Herina rivosecchii*. Fig. 1, ♂, habitus, left; Fig. 2, label; Fig. 3, known distribution (after Kameneva & Greve, 2011).

Kameneva, E.P. (2007) A new species of *Herina* (Diptera, Ulidiidae) from Switzerland, with a key to European species and notes on nomenclature and distribution. *Vestnik zoologii*, 41(5), 405–421.

Kameneva, E. P., Greve, L. (2011) Fauna Europaea: Ulidiidae. In: Pape, T. & Beuk, P. *Fauna Europaea: Diptera Cyclorrhapha. Fauna Europaea version 2.4.* <http://www.faunaeur.org>. – 2011.

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